

Emotional Impact of Source Localization in Music Using Machine Learning and EEG: a proof-of-concept study

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Abstract. Little is currently known about how varied source locations affect a listener's emotional reaction to music. Here, using spectral features extracted from electrophysiology (EEG) data, we tested through machine learning whether four music source positions (front, back, left, and right) could be accurately distinguished according to the type of valence in a subject-wise manner. The findings demonstrate that distinct EEG correlates can reliably classify the four source locations and that the effect is stronger when music with a negative emotional valence is played outside of the listener's visual field. This proof-of-concept study may pave the way for advanced spatial audio analysis approaches in music information retrieval by considering the listener's emotional impact depending on the source direction of incidence.

Keywords: Spatial Music, Emotion Recognition, Affective Computing, EEG, Machine Learning, SVM, Source Localization

1 Introduction

Music's ability to modulate cognitive and emotional processes has been widely documented over the years [1–4], making it a relevant tool to investigate the brain correlates of emotional processes [5]. However, little is known about the impact of different sound-source locations on the emotional response to music, as only a few studies have addressed this issue [6–8]. In particular, the study conducted by Asutay et. al. [7] provided evidence that the effects of spatial source location on attentional processes are mediated by the emotional information conveyed by the sound [7]. The authors also demonstrated that a sound source behind the participant led to a more robust affective response in the listeners [7]. In another work, Tajadura-Jiménez et. al. concluded that

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sound sources outside the visual field produce emotional states of increased arousal [9], though these effects were more pronounced for natural sounds. Similarly, the work of Ekman and Kajastila showed that sounds are judged by the listener as scarier when they come from the back as compared to the front [6], although context has been found to be an important factor in eliciting the desired effect [8]. In a more detailed study using everyday sound events, Drossos et. al [10] showed that lateral positions do increase the listeners' affective state significantly, although this is dependent on the content of the audio sample used.

Moreover, there is a strong connection between space and music, as music can, in turn, evoke sensations of space and movement as a sense of *intrinsic space*, i.e. a metaphorical space, created by musical features in melody, harmony or rhythm, as opposed to the *literal, physical space* a sound source may occupy [11]. The most common effect is that of associating the perceived pitch with a sense of spatial height [12], although alternative spatial representations for the same also exist latently [13]. Furthermore, a correlation between the absolute pitch of a musical piece and emotional affect has been shown [14]. In a study conducted by Eitan et. al. [15], in which participants were asked to associate music with imagined, spatial motions of a human character, it was shown that most musical parameters significantly affect the imaginary motion, indicating a strong correlation between music and space perception.

Here we investigated whether four different music source spatial locations (i.e., front, back, left, and right) are reflected in a distinct pattern of electrophysiological activity that can be captured by a machine-learning approach. Moreover, we explored the interaction between distinct music source locations and the emotional salience of the musical excerpts played. The dimensional model supports the idea that emotions can be modeled as combinations of a few fundamental and basic dimensions. Valence and arousal, sometimes known as the "circumplex model," are two fundamental qualities that researchers unanimously concur are necessary to understand emotions [16]. The valence level varies from unpleasant (negative) to pleasant (positive), while the arousal level, specifically, ranges from not aroused (low arousal) to thrilled (high arousal).

We recorded electrophysiological (EEG) data while participants were listening to musical excerpts characterized by either positive or negative valence, both with middle values of arousal, and occurring from different spatial source locations. To take into account individual differences, we performed subject-based classification between each pair of spatial locations, according to the type of valence. We hypothesized that when the music source was located outside the listener's visual field (i.e., back, right, left) it would lead to a different electrophysiological pattern and impact on the affective state as compared to frontal source localization.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Stimuli

The music excerpts used in this study were taken from the Database for Emotional Evaluation of Music (DEAM) [17]. It features a wide range of musical genres from popular Western styles to spoken word. All excerpts come from royalty-free music sources and

are thus very likely to be unknown to the average participant. In order to choose which samples to use for this study, we categorized the musical excerpts into 3 groups of high, mid, and low values along each emotional dimension (valence and arousal), based on the static evaluation metric. To evaluate the effect of valence in this study, those samples that fell into the mid-arousal category were first selected and then separated into two categories of positive or negative valence. The error between the average dynamic and static rating served as an ordering mechanism, along which the final samples could be selected.

2.2 Experimental design

The sequence of audio samples was arranged into blocks of 3 randomly selected musical excerpts without repetition. Random selection was done anew for each participant. First, from each category, i.e. positive or negative valence, the samples were shuffled and grouped into blocks of 3 musical excerpts. Each block was assigned a spatial position (front, back, left, or right) at random, representing each position equally. Then, the blocks from each category were combined in random order into a single sequence of $36 + 36 = 72$ samples.

The participant was first shown an introduction, explaining the experiment and the SAM questionnaire, followed by a short test if the participant has understood what the SAM represents. Then, a baseline rest period of 120s is recorded. After that, the main experiment started. In each block, 3 music samples from the same spatial position were played. Before each sample, a rest period of 5s was first presented to mentally reset the participant. At the end of each musical sample, the participant had to fill out the SAM questionnaire rating their emotional response to that particular musical stimulus. At the end of each block, another additional questionnaire was shown, where the participant answered how exhausted and attentive they felt.

The experiment ended after all blocks and their respective musical samples had been played to the participant. The EEG data were recorded using a 19-electrode Neuroelectronics® Instrument Controller (NIC2) at a sampling rate of 250 Hz. The subjects were informed about the experimental protocol, its approximate duration, and the meaning of the SAM scales. We instructed the participants not to move, particularly during playback of the stimulus, to reduce muscular artifacts in the EEG data. The experiment was conducted according to the Helsinki Declaration and all subjects signed the consent form.

2.3 Participants

We recruited a total of 20 healthy participants (10 males and 10 females) with a mean age of 28.66 years ($SD = 5.53$), no history of psychiatric or neurological disorders, and normal hearing. Furthermore, subjects had no prior experience or formal music training. Nearly all participants were right-handed, with only one participant being left-handed. After preprocessing the EEG signal, 3 participants were removed from the analysis due to excessive artifacts. Only 17 participants were included in the analysis, comprising 9 females and 8 males with a median age of 28 (20-38).

2.4 Experimental Setup

The room in which the experiment took place was acoustically treated, with acoustic diffusion panels on the walls and absorption panels on the ceiling, as well as acoustically isolated from the outside. The reverberation time was relatively short, with an RT_{60} of 0.398s at 125Hz to 0.253s at 8kHz. The average RT_{60} between 500Hz and 1000Hz is around 0.293s. The audio stimuli were played from four positions: front, back, left, and right. A loudspeaker was placed in each position. The front and back loudspeakers were positioned at 3.2m from the listener, while the side speakers were at 2.3m.

To correct for the differences in distance between the loudspeakers, each loudspeaker was calibrated to 75dB SPL using pink noise at -20 dBFS at the center listening position. The loudspeakers used were of the type Genelec 8040, fed by a Focusrite Scarlet 18i20 soundcard. The audio playback was done with the *sounddevice* module for Python, running on a Windows laptop computer.⁴

The interface was built for a web browser using HTML and CSS, with the functional elements programmed in Javascript and JQuery. The interface was designed with touch controls in mind, filtering accidental double taps and guiding the participant through the experiment. Whenever a button to continue was shown, the participant was also able to change their mind before sending off the result to be recorded. The Python script and the web front-end communicated using a simple socket connection over *localhost*. All activity on the touch screen was recorded over the socket connection.

2.5 EEG preprocessing

EEG data were analyzed in an offline manner using the EEGLAB toolbox on Matlab R2019b (The Mathworks, Inc.). The preprocessing steps included downsampling of the signal to 130 Hz and the application of a bandpass Butterworth filter ranging from 0.01 up to 40 Hz. To correct eye blinks and muscular artifacts, we used the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) algorithm. For each subject, we manually removed all components capturing artifacts. Afterward, we epoched the EEG data and created eight distinct datasets for each subject according to the experimental condition (i.e, spatial position and type of valence). Finally, we applied a spatial filter to reduce the volume conduction effect, using the surface Laplacian transform inspired by the spherical spline method described by [18–20].

2.6 Feature extraction

To preserve information about the temporal dynamics, we transformed the EEG data into the time-frequency domain using Complex Morlet Wavelet convolution (CMW) [21]. We chose CMW instead of alternative approaches like the Short-time Fourier Transform or the Hilbert Transform, because CMW is a Gaussian-shaped wavelet in the frequency domain.

Since we were interested in all frequency bands, we selected a range of frequencies going from 1 Hz up to 40 Hz. Following the use of CMW convolution, we retrieved the

⁴ <https://github.com/multimedia-eurecat/Neuromuse>

power from the coefficients and then used a decibel-baseline normalization, utilizing all neutral trials as a baseline. We used a sliding-window strategy to reduce the time-frequency data for every trial in order to increase the sample size. There were a total of 39 windows in every trial, each lasting 1 second and overlapping by half a second.

Then, we calculated the average change in power compared to the neutral baseline for seven frequency bands (delta 1–4 Hz, theta 4–8 Hz, low alpha 8–10 Hz, high alpha 10–12 Hz, low beta 13–18 Hz, high beta 18–30 Hz, and gamma 31–40 Hz), which constitute the spectral features. Within each window and for all the 19 channels and the seven frequency bands, the features extracted were the mean power, the standard deviation of the mean, and the frontal alpha asymmetry (FAA). The FAA coefficients were calculated for the channel pairs Fp1-Fp2 and F3-F4 in both low-alpha (8–10 Hz) and high-alpha (10–12 Hz) bands. The resulting feature array consisted of 351 samples for each class with a total of 270 features.

2.7 Classification and feature selection

For data classification, we utilized MATLAB R2022a Statistics and the Machine Learning Toolbox. As a base classifier, the linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) supervised learning approach was chosen, which uses a hyperplane as a decision boundary to optimize the margin of separation between two classes. Herewith, SVMs give a metric that permits scaling the certainty with which a window sample is allocated to one of the two classes: the sample's distance from the separation hyperplane. To evaluate the classifier's performance robustly, we used 6-fold cross-validation to train and test the classifier, allocating all windows in one trial to the same fold. Having said that, we also ran the 6-fold cross-validation fifty times and averaged the results across different classification runs.

It is well known that feature extraction and selection strategies assist to reduce computing complexity and develop models with greater generalization capabilities, in addition to enhancing predictive power [22]. That is, we used the Bioinformatics toolbox of MATLAB R2022a to do feature selection due to the large dimensionality of our dataset. The goal was to improve the classifier's learning performance and find the most common discriminative characteristics shared by all participants. We rated the characteristics based on their importance between the classes, using the t-test as an independent criterion for binary classification. For each feature, the built-in function in MATLAB calculates the absolute value of the two-sample t-test with pooled variance estimate. Finally, we identified the top 20 characteristics for each topic and combined them to determine which features were shared by all participants.

Statistical comparisons We used the Wilcoxon rank-sum method to investigate if the SVM performances were significantly above chance, thus we statistically compared accuracy distributions of real-labeled data with surrogate data (i.e., randomly shuffled labels). Furthermore, data from the self-assessment SAM questionnaire were analyzed using a general linear model, the multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA), on IBM SPSS Statistics.

Fig. 1. Within-subject classification results of each binary classification between music position sources according to the type of valence. We performed 6-fold cross-validation 50 times, such that the boxplots depict the results of 50 classification runs for each participant.

3 Results

We investigated through machine learning whether the four music position sources could be accurately differentiated according to the type of valence in a subject-wise manner using spectral features extracted from EEG data cut into 1-second windows. The results of all cross-validation run for each participant are presented in Figure 1. The corresponding accuracy averaged across subjects for each binary classification run is summarized in Table 1. For both positive and negative valence, we showed that the highest average accuracy was reached when classifying the frontal localization versus each of the three sources located outside the visual field. In particular, this effect was stronger when classifying pairs of source locations using events characterized by negative valence.

Table 1. Classification results averaged across participants for each pair of binary classification runs presented according to the valence type. An asterisk indicates that the average accuracy is significantly above the chance level ($p < 0.05$).

	Pair of music source locations	Mean accuracy across subjects		Pair of music source locations	Mean accuracy across subjects
Positive valence	Frontal - Back	70%*	Negative valence	Frontal - Back	85%*
	Frontal - Left	80%*		Frontal - Left	82%*
	Back - Left	69%*		Back - Left	78%*
	Right - Left	76%*		Right - Left	74%*
	Frontal - Right	77%*		Frontal - Right	87%*
	Back - Right	61%*		Back - Right	67%*

3.1 Highest-ranked features

To understand which channels and frequency bands were the most discriminative between the four location sources depending on the type of valence, we applied a feature selection algorithm and merged together the top twenty features for each subject. As represented in Figure 2, the results of the feature selection procedure showed that the electrophysiological correlates of the difference between frontal location and the three sources located outside the visual field (i.e., back, right, left) rely on different activities of channels mainly located in frontal and central areas, especially in the highest frequencies. In particular, we found that when using musical excerpts with negative valence, the difference between frontal location and each of the three sources out of the field of view was based on activity in beta (low and high) and gamma bands in channels Fp1, F3, F4, Fz, Cz, and T8, and in FAA measures for pairs of channels Fp1-Fp2 and F3-F4. On the other side, when comparing the source locations using positive valence, we showed that also brain activity in the alpha band, together with beta and gamma was important for differentiating frontal position from each of the other three sources. Moreover, in the case of positive valence, channels from posterior sites, especially Pz, P7, and P8, as well as central, frontal sites and FAA, were relevant for the classification of source locations, indicating a more widespread involvement of different brain areas.

Fig. 2. Topoplots indicating brain activity for each of the main frequency bands according to the source locations (i.e., front, back, left, and right) and the type of valence (i.e., negative and positive). Colors in brain plots indicate the power in that specific channel and frequency band, with red showing the highest power and blue the lowest.

3.2 Self-assessment SAM questionnaire

Results of self-reported ratings showed that there was a significant difference in arousal and valence ratings based on the type of event (source location and type of valence of musical excerpts), $F(14, 12428) = 28.133$, $p = 0.000$, $Wilk's\lambda = 0.740$,

partial eta squared = 0.14. The source locations depending on the type of valence had a significant effect both on reported levels of perceived arousal, $F(7, 1215) = 18.477$, $p = 0.000$, partial eta squared = 0.096, and valence, $F(7, 1215) = 47.886$, $p = 0.000$, partial eta squared = 0.216. Averaged reported levels of perceived arousal and valence are presented in Table 2.

Post-hoc analysis revealed that there were significant differences between trials with positive valence and negative valence within each source location ($p = 0.000$, Bonferroni corrected). In particular, musical excerpts characterized by positive valence elicited higher reported levels of arousal ($p = 0.000$) and valence ($p = 0.000$) for each of the four source locations. Differences between sources were not significant ($p > 0.05$) when comparing the same type of valence (i.e., either positive or negative), except the levels of reported arousal between the back and right when music with positive valence was played ($p = 0.03$, Bonferroni corrected).

Table 2. Average reported levels of arousal and valence by means of the SAM questionnaire on a Likert scale from 1 to 5.

Type of valence	Source location	Average SAM rating for arousal	Average SAM rating for valence
Positive valence	Frontal	3,41	3,25
	Back	3,57	3,21
	Left	3,22	3,17
	Right	3,45	3,36
Negative valence	Frontal	2,63	2,03
	Back	2,90	2,18
	Left	2,88	2,28
	Right	3,45	2,15

4 Discussion

In this work, we analyzed the impact of different source locations of music depending on the type of valence on the listener's affective brain processing by employing machine learning tools. The results demonstrate that frontal location can be accurately distinguished from each of the three sources (back, right, and left) located outside the listener's visual field. In particular, our results suggested that the emotional connotation of music (i.e., positive and negative valence) mediated the impact of the different source locations on the brain's electrophysiological signal, as reflected by music characterized with negative valence yielding higher classification performances in differentiating between the spatial sources as compared to musical excerpts characterized by positive valence.

Furthermore, by applying a feature selection procedure we showed that playing music from different source locations led to different electrophysiological brain responses in the highest frequencies (alpha, beta, and gamma) and in channels belonging to the frontal, central, and also parietal areas in the case of positive valence. The importance of

beta and gamma bands that we found here is consistent with earlier research showing the significance of these bands for differentiating between various emotional states [23,24]. Moreover, a previous study has found that the alpha band in parietal channels was associated with the processing of auditory stimuli, while the gamma band activity was related to music awareness [25]. Interestingly, we found the FAA between pairs of channels Fp1-Fp2 and F3-F4 to be an important measure for distinguishing between different locations, both for positive and negative valence conditions. Alpha activity in the frontal site has been largely used as an index of emotional processing, reflecting motivation and dominance of perceived emotion. Indeed, in the literature, positive emotional stimuli have been related to a relative increase in left hemisphere activity, whereas negative emotional stimuli have been associated with a larger right hemisphere activity [26,27]. For example, a previous study has found that musical excerpts characterized by positive valence induced lower frontal alpha power in the left hemisphere [28]. In addition to valence and arousal, frontal asymmetry was also linked to other factors, such as self-reported dominance [29].

Music has generally been used in research as a tool to elicit emotional responses in participants and study emotional processes in the brain [30, 31]. Recent applications of Brain-Computer Interfaces have used music as a way to convey information and/or feedback in a real-time manner to the subjects based on their own brain activity [32–34]. However, the difficulty of participants in engaging and sustaining genuine emotional states in an experimental context, particularly when trying to elicit complex emotions, has generally been a significant hurdle for neuroimaging and BCI studies based on affective processes. In this regard, the results of this study may pave the way for more effective use of music as a stimulus in experimental settings.

Moreover, the analysis of tones and their spatial orientation in relation to the listener is relevant in the context of *spatial music*. Here, spatial music refers to musical composition practices that specifically target spatial aspects of sound as a compositional parameter, such as the sound position or specific aspects of room acoustics [35, 36]. Indeed, emotion elicited through spatial music listening is not an aspect that is not often considered in this context. The discussion around space in music tends to be often of philosophical [35], or conceptual nature [36, 37] and often centers around aspects in electronics or hardware [37, 38], technology [39, 40] or taxonomy [41]. In a survey conducted in [42], composers are more often than not concerned with those spatial aspects in music that can be parameterized on a technical level and lesser with the emotional impact space can have on the listener. The results of this study indicate that an analysis of spatial music would need to take into account the correlation between the extracted emotional impact of the more traditional musical parameters, such as melody and rhythm, with the impact made by spatial features.

However, this study does present some limitations. Most importantly, the relatively small sample size may limit the generalization of our results. Also, despite having found a different brain pattern of activity in the EEG signal related to affective processing of music depending on the various source locations, this effect was not reflected in the analysis of subjective ratings of both arousal and valence. This may have been due to overthinking, rather than an immediate and intuitive reaction. When being asked how one would evaluate a piece of music, one would have to execute the said task by rec-

ollecting what was just heard. This evaluation will thus be skewed by the importance a subject might place on different musical aspects. Therefore, if a subject has little to no experience in associating spatial position with musical significance, then the recollection of the heard excerpt will most likely be focused on other aspects, filtering out the spatial direction from which the excerpt was heard. This means that mentally, i.e. in the inner ear, the music may have been heard *aspatially*. Future work may investigate the potential effect that musical training could have on the results in this context.

5 Conclusion

The present study has shown that machine learning methods are able to discern a listener's affective brain processing between different spatial positions of sound sources as a function of positive or negative affect. Annotated musical excerpts were classified into two groups of both median arousal and low or high valence values respectively. These samples were presented to the listener from the front, the lateral left or right positions, or the back, in random order. Our results showed that frontal location, compared to each of the other three sources located outside the visual field, is associated with different brain electrophysiological patterns related to emotional processing. In fact, we found a significant involvement of alpha, beta, and gamma frequency bands in frontal and central sites, together with FAA measures, in distinguishing between such source locations. These findings were not reflected in the subjective rating analysis, hinting that the subjects may have excluded the spatial aspect of the music when consciously evaluating the heard excerpts. While more analysis is necessary, these first results prove promising. Further analysis is necessary to understand how the source location is able to influence the emotional impact of music, particularly focusing on arousal. Also, it would be interesting assessing whether different types of music show divergence in the emotional impact depending on source location. Lastly, future work will also have to include the median plane to get a more comprehensive view of the effects of spatial source locations on the listener's affective state.

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